

Kinetics of Oxidation of Aromatic Aldehydes by Manganese (III) Acetate

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The kinetics of the oxidation of benzaldehyde and four substituted benzaldehydes have been studied in 95% (v/v) acetic acid. The reaction velocity is of first order with respect to both [Aldehyde] and [Manganese(III)]. The reaction velocity increased with increase of acid concentration. The reaction rate is unaffected by Mn(II) ions. The rate decreases with increasing the proportion of water in the reaction mixture. A probable mechanism has been suggested for the reaction.

Mn(III) is one of the group of metal ion oxidants which apparently react via one-electron steps¹. Oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by one and two electron oxidants has been reported in the literature. Cooper and Waters² have studied the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by cobaltic salts. Anantakrishnan and Jayaraman³ have reported the oxidation of some *m*- and *p*-substituted aromatic aldehydes by Cr(VI). Very recently, Wiberg and co-workers⁴ have reported the Ce(IV) oxidation of some aromatic aldehydes. In the present case, the kinetics of the Mn(III) acetate oxidation of some aromatic aldehydes has been reported.

Materials and Methods

Analytical reagent grade benzaldehyde was distilled in nitrogen through a short Vigreux column and the middle fraction collected. Other liquid benzaldehydes were purified similarly immediately before kinetic runs. Solid aldehydes were washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and recrystallised from ethanol-water to constant m.p. Acetic acid used was of B.D.H. Analar grade. Manganese triacetate was prepared from manganous acetate and potassium permanganate by the method of Dewar⁵.

Stoichiometry and Product Analysis

Stoichiometry was determined in the usual way with excess of Mn(III) which was estimated after the reaction was over. The stoichiometry was calculated to be 2:1 [Δ Mn(III)]/ Δ benzaldehyde]. The reaction occurs according to the following equation:

After purification by conventional methods the solid obtained from the reaction mixture gave a melting point 122°. The yield was quantitative.

The formation of a free radical was proved by carrying out a few reactions in the presence of acrylamide when the latter polymerised.

The reaction was followed by our previous method⁶ by estimating the unreacted Mn(III) by iodometric procedure. The rate of constants were computed with an accuracy of 1-2% error in duplicate runs.

Dependence on [Aldehyde] and [Mn(III)]

The reaction velocity is of first order with respect to both [aldehyde] and [manganese(III)]. The results have been reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Acidity

The reaction rate increases with increase of perchloric acid concentration. Plot of $\log k$ versus Hammett's acidity function (H_0) is linear showing the applicability of Zucker-Hammett treatment⁷.

Effect of substituent on rate

A point of great interest in mechanistic studies is the influence of substituent groups. It is found that electron withdrawing groups accelerate the rate of oxidation and electron releasing groups retard it. The observed rate conform to the following order:

The same order of substituent effect has been observed by Anantakrishnan and co-workers⁵ for the Cr(VI) oxidation and Waters² for the Co(III) oxidation of aromatic aldehydes.

$\rho\sigma$ -plot

Correlation of the rate constants with σ^+ substituent constants gave a ρ^+ of +0.25 with correlation coefficient $r = 0.994$ and standard deviation $s = 0.0375$.

Isokinetic relationship

A linear relationship between the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and the enthalpy of activation

TABLE 1. DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [Mn(III)].

[Benzaldehyde] × 10 ² = 6.25 (M); Solvent : 95% (vol/vol) Acetic acid,	[HClO ₄] × 10 = 1.5 (M) Temp. = 35°							
[Mn(III)] × 10 ³ M	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	5.75	5.74	5.69	5.65	5.59	5.70	5.72	5.74

TABLE 2. DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [BENZALDEHYDE]

[Mn(III)] × 10 ² = 5 (M); Solvent : 95% (vol/vol) Acetic acid;	[HClO ₄] × 10 = 1.5 (M) Temp. = 35°				
[Benzaldehyde] × 10 ²	2.50	3.75	5.00	8.75	11.25
k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	2.44	3.66	4.75	8.32	10.69
$\frac{k_1 \times 10^5}{[\text{Benzaldehyde}]}$ 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	0.98	0.98	0.95	0.95	0.95
[Benzaldehyde] × 10 ²	12.50		17.50	18.75	
k ₁ × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	12.12		16.89	17.78	
$\frac{k_1 \times 10^5}{[\text{Benzaldehyde}]}$ 1.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	0.97		0.97	0.95	

k average in 1.mole⁻¹sec⁻¹ = 0.961 × 10⁻³.

TABLE 3. DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON THE CONCENTRATION OF ACID

[Benzaldehyde] × 10 ² , M = 6.25; Solvent = 95% (vol/vol) Acetic acid;	[Mn(III)] × 10 ³ = 5.0 (M) Temp. = 35°						
[H ⁺] × 10, M	1.50	2.00	2.25	2.50	2.75	3.00	3.50
k × 10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹	5.75	6.49	7.68	9.21	10.28	11.23	12.50
$\frac{k \times 10^4}{[\text{H}^+]}$	3.83	3.24	3.41	3.68	3.48	3.74	3.57

(ΔH[‡]) has been observed for the Mn(III) oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes. The data can be fitted in the equation⁸, ΔH[‡] = ΔH₀[‡] + βΔS[‡]. ΔH₀[‡] has the value 21.20 K.Cal/mole and β has the value 573°K for the reaction. The linear relationship shown by the majority of substituted benzaldehydes indicates that apparently the same mechanism prevails in all the cases⁹.

Effect on Mn(II) on rate

The rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde has been studied in various Mn(II) concentrations. Mn(II) solutions may contain some Mn(IV) species as well. If oxidation due to Mn(IV) species is important then addition of Mn(II) should alter the rate in accordance with the equation

Since Mn(II) has no effect in the reaction, Mn(III) is the only oxidising species.

Effect of change of composition of solvent

The rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde increases with increasing proportion of acetic acid in acetic acid-water solvents. The reaction rate increasing with decrease in dielectric constant shows the nature of process as a positive ion-dipole reaction¹⁰.

According to Amis and Jaffe¹¹ theory, if the dielectric constant is increased, the rate should decrease for a positive ion-dipole reaction. Laidler-Eyring¹² theory also predicts increase of rate constant with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium for a reaction between dipole and any ion (positive or negative). A plot of log k vs. 1/D shows linearity. Hence our findings are in agreement with both the theories.

Discussion

The oxidation of benzaldehyde to benzoic acid by Mn(III) may be schematically represented as follows :

TABLE 4. INFLUENCE OF Mn(II) ON RATE

$[\text{Benzaldehyde}] \times 10^2 = 11.25$; $[\text{Mn(III)}] \times 10^3 = 5.0$
 $[\text{H}^+] \times 10 = 1.5 (M)$; Solvent : 95% (vol/vol) Acetic acid
 Temp. = 35°

$[\text{Mn(III)}] \times 10^3, M$	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.0	10.69
2.0	10.70
3.0	10.53
4.0	10.10

TABLE 5. EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON RATE

$[\text{Benzaldehyde}] \times 10^2 = 11.25 (M)$; $[\text{Mn(II)}] \times 10^3 = 5.0 (M)$
 $[\text{H}^+] \times 10 = 1.5 (M)$; Temp. = 35°

HOAc : H ₂ O (v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
95	10.69
90	9.40
85	8.60
80	7.73
70	6.23

TABLE 6. EFFECT OF SUBSTITUENT ON RATE

Substrate	$k \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$			E K.Cal/mole	-ΔS‡ e.u.
	35°	40°	45°		
H	5.75	9.21	15.36	20.50	13.50
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	6.14	10.75	16.66	17.30	23.80
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	11.52	19.19	34.53	14.30	32.20
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	5.00	8.23	14.89	21.40	10.80
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	4.60	7.67	13.05	23.00	5.70

The reaction scheme represented in (1) thus involves removal of one electron from the organic substrate. This occurs more rapidly with the electron withdrawing groups than with electron donating groups, although nitro-groups are electrophilic and might be expected to hinder such electron removal. The greater reactivity of nitro compounds can reasonably be ascribed to the greater degree of resonance stabilisation of the radical $\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{CO}\cdot$ than of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{CO}\cdot$.

Equation (1) represents the oxidation process which occurs, but it gives no indication of the way in which the homolysis of the C-H bond is effected. To explain the course of the oxidation step the following mechanism may be suggested.

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